

Digitisation of Information Resources in Academic Libraries in Bayelsa State: Challenges and Prospects

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Abstract

The paper investigated the digitisation of information resources in academic libraries in Bayelsa State. The study was carried out in the libraries of the Niger Delta University (NDU), Federal University Otuoke (FUO), University of Africa Toru-Orua (UOA) and Bayelsa Medical University Yenagoa (BMU), all in Bayelsa State. The population and sample of this study comprised 40 academic librarians in the libraries of the above-mentioned institutions. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Five objectives and five research questions were set for the study; a structured questionnaire was used to collect data. To analyse the data, the following descriptive statistical measures were employed: frequency table, simple percentage and a 4-point Likert-type scale. A criterion mean of 2.5 and above was accepted as a positive response; 2.4 and below was rejected. This paper establishes that there are challenges militating against the digitisation of information materials in academic libraries, such as poor funding of digitisation projects, inadequate staff capacity to manage the process of digitisation, intellectual property rights, infrastructure to support the digitisation process, and users' dependence solely on traditional library resources, among others. Prospects to address these challenges include increased funding of the library budget, staff skill development in the management of digital libraries, copyright that should exclude digitisation practices by librarians, inclusion of digitisation sections when planning for library buildings, and library user education that should include skills needed for the use of digital libraries, among others. The study concluded that digitisation will enable university libraries to preserve endangered library resources, improve the efficiency of information search mechanisms and enhance access to library resources.

Keywords: Digitisation, Information resources, Academic Libraries, Bayelsa State

Introduction

For a long time, libraries have shaped our society by strategically generating, organising and making available to human use knowledge from a variety of local, regional, national and international sources, to the extent that their importance has ensured their survival throughout their long history. It is a known fact that libraries have witnessed significant changes in recent years. This change, brought about by information and communication technologies, has impacted the way information services are provided. In that regard, the acquisition, organisation, maintenance, and provision of information to users began to take on a more coherent form as information was encoded in the universal language of computers. This process had to emerge from the vast amount of information produced worldwide, which comes in a wide variety of formats: text, databases, audio, video, and images. Cultural institutions entrusted with collecting and preserving cultural heritage had to think quickly about how best to manage the stream of information available for the consumption of present and future generations. This is because their failure

to do so may lead to a series of losses unless specific techniques and policies are developed to conserve them. Interestingly, most enterprises, from libraries to small businesses, large corporations, non-profit organisations, and government agencies, had to leap into digital transformation by computerising their processes and activities and recording their transactions.

The traditional methods of information dissemination have given way to electronic means of communication. While the developments and applications of ICT in library operations have improved information dissemination and access, they have also created new roles in information provision, dissemination, and transfer. The librarian is no longer a custodian of books but the gateway to a myriad of information sources. Pandey & Misra (2014) posit that while providing books was a standalone function for libraries throughout the last few centuries, their offerings have evolved with the digital age to meet the changing needs of their patrons. Academic libraries in Nigeria are not divorced from this technological revolution. As information providers, they are constantly under pressure to deliver relevant information to their immediate communities. Technology enables change and enforces it. In other words, as it became more arduous for libraries to acquire, organise, preserve and offer their users the multifarious documented knowledge available to them, they resorted to a medium capable of fostering better, faster and more reliable services, courtesy of ICTs. The adoption of these technologies into our daily activities has brought about a complete modification in the way we work, shop, communicate, bank, govern, travel, educate, etc., as digitisation has paved the way for the conversion of traditional forms of information storage, such as paper and photographs, into the binary code of computer storage, via a subset of converting analogue signals into digital ones. However, the emergence of the World Wide Web in 1993 and its rapid development thereafter have allowed developers to provide universal access to digital libraries (Jha, 2012, as cited in Nneji, 2018).

Now, in the 21st century, with the emergence of ICT and Web 2.0 technologies, libraries have a new, more dynamic role in the knowledge society. As individuals are affected by ICT, they can also influence the technology (Brindley, 2009). Libraries began to recognise the web experience and utilised such services to create a new environment for users in which interaction plays a central role. Interaction means that technology engages with the social world, its values, and beliefs (Brindley, 2009). These services have also transformed academic libraries, which face greater demand for access to resources; they should store all kinds of materials in various formats; librarians have crucial duties and roles in disseminating and sharing knowledge; and users need to transfer information both inside and outside the walls of a library. Hence, university libraries would be upgraded and become digital.

Digital libraries, institutional repositories, and open archives are the new trend in the present era, meeting users' needs for precise information as users have become more information-conscious about accessing electronic information for various purposes, including academic and research needs. According to Fabunmi, Paris, and Fabunmi (2006), library digitisation has become part of librarians' work, and most libraries are involved in digitisation projects. Developments in digital technology have influenced academic libraries in most developed and developing countries, contributing to their overall improvement. Academic libraries use digital technology to manage user services, communication facilities, housekeeping operations, and the standardisation and development of library activities. Academic libraries need to respond to the growing and diversifying information needs of end users (Anuradha, 2017). The advent of the digital era in libraries necessitated the computerisation of most operations. Technology has changed the way traditional librarians used to work. Nowadays, librarians use technology to acquire, catalogue, preserve, disseminate, and provide reference services, among other tasks. This doesn't mean that traditional libraries will cease to exist. Traditional libraries, as buildings, will continue

to exist for many years and support digital libraries. Thus, traditional and digital libraries co-exist. This means that librarians play, and will continue to play, a significant role in libraries. It is important for librarians to maintain a balance between their traditional and digital roles (Anuradha, 2017).

In Nigeria, most first-generation university libraries, such as the Kenneth Dike Library at the University of Ibadan, have established digital links with the following digital collections: Access to Global Online Research in Agriculture (AGORA); Journal Storage (JSTOR); Health Inter Network Access to Research Initiative (HINARI); The Essential Electronic Agricultural Library (TEEAL); Eliot B. Stephens Company (EBSCO); E-Granary Digital Library; Highwire Archive; International Network for Advancing Science and Policy (INASP); Program for the Enhancement of Research Information (Peril); African Journals Online; Arab Social Science Research Virtual Library (ASSR); Biomed Central; BMJ Publishing Group; British Library for Development Studies E-Journals; Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ); E-Journal.org; Global Development Network-Journal Services; INASP Health Links; Population Information Online (POPLINE); and PubMed Central Research Papers in Economics (PEPEC). Although the preservation of materials is the ultimate goal of all digitisation efforts, providing greater access is another noble reason to digitise library collections. Most third-world libraries depend on books from Europe and America, and these books are very expensive for them to procure. Creating a digital library is a very expensive venture that requires adequate planning and monitoring. Digitisation is time-consuming and very expensive.

Digitisation

Libraries hold vast amounts of information and knowledge in their collections. As we know, many physical collections are kept in the library, which requires considerable space. Since the early 2000s, most libraries have embarked on digitisation initiatives. Digitisation is the process of converting physical documents, such as sound, paper, or images, into an electronic form that can be read by computers or other electronic devices. These records are then made available via the Internet. One of the main purposes of this initiative is to preserve the library's physical collection. By doing so, the library has implemented added-value services for its users. For example, the Utusan Melayu Information Centre started its digitisation initiative in 2004. The act of digitisation can be viewed as a process of preserving items through selection, acquisition, preparation, and data capture of documents, sounds, or images via any electronic device capable of capturing text, sound, or images, for onward storage, access, and transmission to a digital platform. Nneji (2018), citing Arora (2010), defines digitisation as the process of translating a piece of information, such as a book, journal article, sound recording, picture, audio tape, or video recording, into bits. The author explains further that bits are the fundamental units of information in a computer system, and that converting information into these binary digits is called digitisation, which can be achieved through a variety of existing technologies.

Digitisation is the process of representing an object, an image, or a signal (usually an analogue signal) as a discrete set of points or samples. The author further explains that a distinction is often made between content created in digital format (Jha, 2012, as cited in Nneji, 2018). Digital library resources can be converted to formats such as .pdf, .jpeg, or .bmp. This method of maintaining library collections is more manageable. In terms of space utilisation, the entire collection is stored on a server and can be accessed via the library website once indexing and cataloguing are complete. Backups must be made to keep the records safe. Backups can be performed internally or externally. One notable feature after the implementation of digitisation is the creation of e-book formats. E-books can be classified as part of the

library's digital collection. Users can easily download e-books from the library portal to their smartphones or tablets.

Statement of Problem

Previous studies reveal that few libraries in Nigeria have embarked on digitising their collections. There remains a significant gap in the availability of current information on the digitisation efforts of Nigerian university libraries. There is, therefore, a need to provide up-to-date information on the digitisation of academic library resources in Nigerian university libraries through research of this nature.

Digitisation of library resources has been conceived as a means for libraries to increase their relevance in this contemporary era of information and communication technology (ICT) and has been observed to be significant in budgetary and cost management. This is evidenced by the rapid pace of information growth and the availability of information via the internet, irrespective of time and location. For libraries to co-exist and maintain their relevance as information disseminators in this era, the digitisation of library resources is indispensable for librarians. Thus, with identifiable benefits evident in the digitisation of library resources in the acquisition, organisation, dissemination, access, use, preservation, and conservation of information resources, libraries in Nigeria still seem to be on the bench in the drive towards achieving a digitised collection.

This has become a pressing issue in the library and information service profession. Consequently, it is necessary to investigate the status quo of the digitisation of library resources in academic libraries in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, using the Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island; Federal University, Otuoke; University of Africa, Toru-Orua; and Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa, as study areas.

Objectives of the Study

In general, the purpose of the study is to examine the digitisation of library resources in academic libraries in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. To determine the need for digitisation of library resources;
- ii. To examine the extent of digitisation of library resources in academic libraries;
- iii. To ascertain the skills and competencies required for the digitisation of library resources;
- iv. To identify the challenges of the digitisation of academic library resources;
- v. To proffer measures to combat issues in the digitisation of library resources

Literature Review

In response to threats to libraries in this ICT era, such as the internet, the primary objective of every library has become digitising its resources. The term digitisation has attracted considerable research interest over the years. Digitisation refers to the conversion of content from a tangible, analogue form into a digital electronic representation. Omotayo and Aboyade (2009) assert that “digitisation refers to all the steps involved in the process of making collections of historical and other materials available online”. They further state that digitisation is not limited to libraries but also applies to other categories of information dissemination centres. Digitisation addresses three main needs of libraries (Tuna, Zogo and Demirelli, 2013, as cited in Nneji, 2018): preserving the document, making it more accessible, and ensuring its reusability.

Digitisation is the electronic process of converting information from a print format to a digital format (Egberongbe, 2016). Igwe and Uzuegbu (2013) defined digitisation as “the transformation of an object from analogue to digital.” They further noted that, during the ICT era, several new technologies have emerged and continue to emerge, enabling the digitisation of various information formats, such as artefacts, documents, photographs, sound recordings, etc. Quoting Akintunde and Anjo (2012), Igwe and Uzuegbu (2013) defined digitisation as the process of preserving, liberalising and internationalising access to documents, with the ultimate aim of improving their usability by converting them into digital form. Fabumi, Paris and Fabumi (2008) defined digitisation as “the conversion of documents and art into digital images”.

Thus, from the definitions provided by these authors, it can be deduced that digitisation is a planned and systematic process of transforming hard copies of information resources into electronic formats, such as soft copies. Planning is the foundation of every successful project, whether library-related or otherwise. In planning the digitisation of library resources, it is pertinent to incorporate the provisions and limitations of copyright law into the process. Igwe and Uzuegbu (2013) identified five needs behind the digitisation of library resources in libraries: 1. Preservation, 2. Accessibility 3. Resource sharing and service delivery 4. Prestige and visibility 5. Technological development.

- **Preservation:** According to Reitz (2004), preservation is the prolonging of the existence of library and archival materials by maintaining them in a condition suitable either for their original form or for a more durable form, such as digitisation. There is a need to preserve information resources through digitisation, especially for materials in limited supply, such as manuscripts, diaries, and grey literature. Digitisation reduces manual handling, thereby limiting mutilation by external forces and prolonging the lifespan of such materials.
- **Accessibility:** Access to and use of its materials are easy, regardless of location. Digitisation facilitates access to information resources and improves the efficiency of information search mechanisms. This is because digitised resources are available online, irrespective of location. Digital documents/files can be accessed, retrieved and reused by anyone over a wider area than in a manual/analogue library.
- **Resource Sharing and Service Delivery:** According to Feather and Sturges (2003), resource sharing is “a mode of co-operation where library resources and functions are shared in common by a number of libraries”. Igwe and Uzuegbu (2013) assert that it is an activity that results from an agreement, formal or informal, among libraries, usually a consortium or library network, to share collections, data, facilities, and personnel for the benefit of their users and to reduce the expense of collection development. Digitisation offers the advantage of providing a platform for data duplication and library networking.
- **Prestige and visibility:** Digitisation can bring prestige, respect, and visibility to a collection of information resources that is unique and of global importance. This is true because information on the internet is viral, unlike that in a library with controlled access and usage.
- **Technological development:** The availability of technological advancements in ICT calls for libraries and information centres to embrace the drives in technological development to their benefit. Thus, digitisation is a contributory factor in the development of the ICT era.

Methodology

A descriptive survey method was used for this study. The study was carried out in the libraries of the Niger Delta University (NDU), Federal University Otuoke (FUO), University of Africa Toru-Orua (UOA)

and Bayelsa Medical University Yenagoa (BMU), all in Bayelsa State. The target population of this study was 40 academic librarians in the libraries of the above-mentioned institutions. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The researcher used research assistants (a librarian at each institution except BMU) to administer and retrieve the 40 copies of the questionnaire from respondents within a five-day interval. This was done to ensure a quick return and to minimise loss of completed questionnaires. All copies of the questionnaire were found usable and were used. The researcher used descriptive statistical tools to analyse each item in the questionnaire to match the research objectives. For responses on a 4-point Likert-type scale, a criterion mean of 2.5 and above was accepted as a positive response, and 2.4 and below was rejected.

Data Analysis Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Institutions and Respondents

S/N	Institution	Respondents	Percentage
1	Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island	21	52.5
2	Federal University, Otuoke	12	30.0
3	University of Africa, Toru-Orua	6	15.0
4	Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa	1	2.5
	Total	40	100

Table 1 shows that 21 of the respondents were from Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island; 12 from the Federal University, Otuoke; 6 from the University of Africa, Toru-Orua; and 1 from Bayelsa Medical University.

Table 2: Gender of the Respondents

S/N	Gender of Respondents	Male	Female
1	Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island	10	11
2	Federal University, Otuoke	5	7
3	University of Africa, Toru-Orua	2	4
4	Bayelsa Medical University, Yenagoa	1	0
	Total	18 (45%)	22 (55%)

Table 2 shows that a total of 18 (45%) of the respondents from all the studied institutions were male, while 22(55%) were female.

Academic qualification of the respondents

Table 3. Percentage of responses on the academic qualifications of respondents

S/N	Academic Qualification	Respondents	Percentage
1	Ph.D	10	25.0
2	Master	11	27.5
3	Bachelor's/HND	19	47.5
	Total	40	100

Table 3 above shows that 10 (25.0%) of the respondents held a PhD. Master's degree holders were 11 (27.5%), while librarians with a bachelor's degree or a high national diploma were 19 (47.5%).

Years of Experience of the Respondents

Table 4. Percentages of responses on the years of experience of respondents

S/N	Years of Experience	Respondents	Percentage
1	1 – 5	3	7.5
2	6 – 10	11	27.5
3	11 – 15	18	45.0
4	16 – 35	8	20.0
	Total	40	100

From the results presented in Table 4 above, the majority of respondents, 18 (45.0%), were in the 11-15 years of working experience bracket. This was closely followed by 11 (27.5%) in the 6-10 years bracket, 8 (20.0%) in the 16-35 years bracket, and 3 (7.5%) in the 1-5 years bracket.

Digitisation of Library Resources

Table 5. The need for digitisation of library resources N = 40, Criterion mean = 2.5

s/n	Item	SA	A	D	SD	X	Decision
1	To preserve endangered library resources	22	18	--	--	3.23	Accepted
2	To increase visibility of institutional outputs	25	15	--	--	3.77	Accepted
3	To embrace the benefits of information and communication technologies	22	18	--	--	3.23	Accepted
4	To enhance timeless access to library information resources	31	9	--	--	3.62	Accepted
5	To displace the role of librarians in library services	--	--	9	31	1.54	Rejected
6	To promote interlibrary cooperation	23	17	--	--	3.39	Accepted

Table 5 above shows the mean responses regarding the need for digitising library resources. The results indicate that the mean response for “to preserve endangered library resources” is 3.23, while the mean response for “to increase visibility of institutional outputs” is 3.77. The mean response for “to embrace the benefits of information and communication technologies” is 3.23, while the mean response for “to enhance timeless access to library information resources” is 3.62. The mean response for “to displace the role of librarians in library services” has the lowest score at 1.54, while the mean response for “to promote interlibrary cooperation” is 3.39. The study revealed that many factors drive the need for digitisation of library resources; these include improved library services, increased access, faster document retrieval, effective preservation, and simultaneous search. This is quite revealing, and the findings show that the digitisation of library resources is indispensable in the present digital environment. These findings corroborate those of Igwe and Uzuegbu (2013), who stated the needs behind the digitisation of library resources in libraries as preservation of endangered materials, increased accessibility to library resources, resource sharing and service delivery among libraries in a consortium, enhanced prestige and visibility of the library, and promotion of technological development in library services.

Extent of Digitisation

Table 6. The extent of digitisation of library resources in the library N = 40, Criterion mean = 2.5

S/N	Item	VHE	HE	ME	LE	X	Decision
1	Co-operating with other libraries on a digital library network	22	18	--	--	3.23	Accepted
2	Have just established and are running a digital library	22	18	--	--	3.23	Accepted
3	Completed an in-house digitisation of library resources such as theses, dissertations and project reports	23	17	--	--	3.39	Accepted
4	Planning for a maiden digitisation of library resources	--	--	15	25	1.39	Rejected
5	Still dependent on the analogue/traditional system of librarianship	--	--	23	17	2.23	Rejected

The results show that the mean responses for “co-operating with other libraries on a digital library network” and for “have just established and running a digital library” are both 3.23. The mean response for “have completed an in-house digitisation of library resources” is 3.39. The mean response for “Planning for a maiden digitisation of library resources” is 1.39, while that for “still dependent on analogue/traditional system of librarianship” is 2.23. The study’s findings on the extent of digitisation of library resources revealed that theses, dissertations, and project reports are the main resources being digitised in the libraries under study. The results also indicated that the library already has an established digital library and a library network with other libraries. This shows that the university library is embarking on digitising its local content. The digitised materials comprise what has been produced within the institutions, e.g., theses and dissertations, research reports, papers presented at conferences, and journal articles written by members of the academic staff. The findings are in line with the study carried out by Usman (2007) on the status of digitisation in 30 Nigerian University libraries, which revealed that Nigerian universities are lagging behind in the pace of digitisation of their question papers, theses, and dissertations. On the other hand, the findings of this study revealed that efforts are underway to digitise these materials.

Librarians Skills and Competence

Table 7. Librarians’ skills and competencies in the digitisation of library resources. N = 40, Criterion mean = 2.5

s/n	Item	SA	A	D	SD	X	Decision
1	Ability to use the computer system	17	23	--	--	3.15	Accepted
2	Ability to convert traditional library resources into digital images	31	9	--	--	3.62	Accepted
3	Ability to develop system software for the digitisation of library resources	17	23	--	--	3.15	Accepted
4	Ability to establish, run and maintain a digital library database	27	13	--	--	3.46	Accepted
5	Ability to make use of the web and electronic databases	27	13	--	--	3.46	Accepted

The results show that the mean response for librarians' ability to use the computer system is 3.15, while the mean for the ability to convert traditional library resources into digital images is 3.62. The mean response for librarians' ability to develop system software for digitising library resources is 3.15. The results also show that the mean response for the ability to establish, run, and maintain a digital library database is 3.46, while the mean for the ability to use the web and electronic databases is also 3.46. Having identified the need for digitising library resources and the institution's digitisation efforts, the study further examined the skills and competencies of library staff to meet the requirements of the digitisation process. The findings revealed that librarians possessed a good number of the prerequisite skills for digitising library resources. The skills and competencies ranged from the ability to use the computer system, to the ability to convert traditional library resources into digital images, to the ability to develop system software for the digitisation of library resources, to the ability to establish, run and maintain a digital library database, and to the ability to make use of the web and electronic databases. Due to the changing nature of the library environment, educating librarians to acquire digitisation skills in the dynamic and complex digital environment has become a high priority within library and information science schools. These findings support the earlier research output of Sreenivasulu (1998), who categorised the needed skills for the digitisation of library resources as internet skills, multimedia skills, and digital information skills (cited in Igwesi, 2010).

Challenges to Digitisation

Table 8. Challenges to digitization of library resources N = 40, Criterion mean = 2.5

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	X	Decision
1	Funding of digitisation projects	27	13	--	--	3.46	Accepted
2	Staff capacity to manage the process of digitisation	25	15	--	--	3.77	Accepted
3	Intellectual property rights	23	17	--	--	3.39	Accepted
4	Infrastructure to contain the digitisation process	22	18	--	--	3.23	Accepted
5	Users depend solely on traditional library resources	24	16	--	--	3.54	Accepted
6	Hardware and software obsolescence	24	16	--	--	3.54	Accepted
7	Power supply	24	16	--	--	3.54	Accepted
8	Security of databases	23	17	--	--	3.39	Accepted

The results show that the mean response to funding digitisation projects is 3.46, while the mean response to staff capacity to manage the process is 3.77. The mean response for intellectual property rights is 3.39. The results also show that the mean response for infrastructure supporting the digitisation process is 3.23, while the mean response for users who rely solely on traditional library resources is 3.54. The table shows that the mean response for hardware and software obsolescence is 3.54, and for power supply it is 3.54. The mean response for database security is 3.39.

Despite the inherent benefits of digitising library resources, the results revealed problems that militate against digitisation, including funding for digitisation projects, staff capacity to manage the digitisation process, intellectual property rights, infrastructure to support the digitisation process, users' dependence on traditional library resources, hardware and software obsolescence, power supply, and database security. These findings are consistent with the reports by Umar and Shittu (2014) and Yaya and Adeeko (2016) on the challenges of digitisation in libraries. This shows that a very serious effort should be made to curb these problems.

Suggested Solutions to the Challenges

Table 9. Solutions to the challenges to digitisation of library resources N = 40, Criterion mean = 2.5

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	X	Decision
1	Management should increase the library budget quota	23	17	--	--	3.39	Accepted
2	Staff skill development in the management of digital libraries	24	16	--	--	3.54	Accepted
3	Copyright should exclude digitisation practices by librarians	18	22	--	--	3.31	Accepted
4	Inclusion of digitisation sections while planning for library buildings	24	16	--	--	3.54	Accepted
5	Library user education should include skills needed for the use of digital libraries	31	9	--	--	3.62	Accepted
6	Update of software data applications and hardware devices	18	22	--	--	3.31	Accepted
7	Installation of an alternative power supply, such as a standby power-generating set, etc.	23	17	--	--	3.39	Accepted
8	Installation of anti-virus, malware and hack-proof software	31	9	--	--	3.62	Accepted

The results show that the mean response to “management should increase the library budget quota” is 3.39, while the mean response to “staff skill development in management of digital libraries” is 3.54. The table further shows that the mean response to “copyright should exclude digitisation practices by librarians” is 3.31, while the mean response to “inculcating digitisation sections while planning for library buildings” is 3.54. The results show that the mean response to “library user education should include skills needed for use of digital libraries” is 3.62, while the mean response to the update of software data applications and hardware devices is 3.31. The mean response to the installation of alternative power supplies, such as standby power generating sets, solar power systems, utility power systems, etc., is 3.39, while the mean response to the installation of anti-virus, malware, and hack-proof software is 3.62.

In response to the challenges of digitising library resources, the respondents agreed that all the strategies proposed by the researcher, ranging from soliciting increased funding for the library budget, staff skill development in the management of digital libraries, excluding digitisation practices by librarians, including digitisation sections when planning library buildings, ensuring library user education covers the skills needed to use digital libraries, updating software, data applications, and hardware devices, installing alternative power supplies such as standby power-generating sets, solar power systems, and utility power systems, and installing antivirus, antimalware, and hack-proof software, are appropriate approaches for effective digitisation. Prior to these findings, Ibinaiye (2012) suggested that library management can provide effective solutions to the problems faced in the digitisation unit by purchasing additional equipment for services such as digital cameras, Photoshop software, and a standby power-generating set, standardising supplied paper sizes and CD-ROMs, and upgrading systems to meet the needs of modern-day technologies. Usman (2007) noted that in the digitisation process, “planning involves identifying various tasks related to creating a digital library collection, developing strategies for handling these tasks,

identifying required resources and formulating a timeline for accomplishing these tasks". Hazen (1998), in agreement with this, contends that to achieve effective digitisation, it is imperative to set up a committee to draft a plan and a policy that establishes the goals and objectives, selection criteria, availability of funds, infrastructure, and personnel requirements. From the foregoing, it is imperative to make an adequate plan before embarking on any digitisation exercise.

Conclusion

Digital libraries have reduced the burden on librarians and students alike. The concept of digital library software is quite old, but it is becoming more popular as new technologies are adopted. It is necessary to stay up to date with new technologies, which will enhance students' learning and build their skills and confidence to face challenges. The role of the DL emphasises the multimedia nature of the next generation of digital libraries, requiring digital librarians (DL) to be essentially specialist librarians who manage and organise the digital library, handle specialised tasks such as large-scale digitisation, storage, access, digital knowledge mining, digital reference services, electronic information services, search coordination, and manage the archive and its access. The digital librarian acts as a guardian of the information superhighway, the universal digital library, or the global digital library, and as a symbiotic human-machine guru (Sreenivasulu, 2000).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University libraries should seek more financial aid from international philanthropic organisations, like the MacArthur Foundation, the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, etc., as well as from the Federal Government through TETFUND, to include digitisation projects in the library intervention fund every year for each library.
2. There should be provision of on-the-job training and more refresher courses for the library staff's skill development on digitisation processes. In addition, regular staff training through seminars, workshops, conferences, refresher courses, and in-service training should be institutionalised as part of the digitisation project's development plan.
3. Alternative power supply should be provided, such as procuring high-capacity generators and the use of solar systems, in order to mitigate the problem of epileptic power supply from the national grid.
4. Procurement of software packages that will be most suitable for the digitisation project, to help ensure the effective digitisation of library resources.

References

- Anuradha, P. (2017). The impact of digital technologies on academic libraries: challenges and opportunities. *IP Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology*, 2(2), 46-50
- Brindley, L.J. (2009). Challenges for great libraries in the age of the digital native. *Information Services & Use*, 29(1), pp.3-12.
- Egberongbe, H. S. (2016). Digital resources utilisation by social science researchers in Nigerian universities. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. Paper 1424. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1424>

- Fabunmi, B. A., Paris, M. and Fabunmi, M. (2006). Digitisation of library resources: Challenges and implications for policy and planning. *International Journal of Africa America Studies*, 5(2), pp. 23–36.
- Feather, J. and Sturges, R. P. (2003). *International Encyclopaedia of Information and Library Science*. 2nd ed. Routledge, pp. 138
- Hazen, D., Horrell, J. & Merrill-Oldham, J. (1998). Selecting record collections for digitisation. *Council on library and information resources*. www.clir.org/pubs/reports/hazen/pub74.htm
- Ibinaiyé, D. I. (2012). Challenges and prospects of digitisation of library resources in Nigerian universities: The experience of Kashim Ibrahim Library. *European Journal of Globalisation and Development Research*, 5(1)18
- Igwe, K. N. & Uzuegbu, C. P. (2013). *Automation in libraries and information centres*. Zeh Communication Ltd. p.37
- Igwesi, U (2010). Status of digitisation of Federal University libraries in South-Eastern Zone, *Nigeria*. An unpublished MLS project submitted to the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Nneji, K. O. (2018). Digitisation of academic library resources: A case study of Donal E. U. Ekong Library. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 1990. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1990>
- Omotayo, E. A. & Aboyade, A. (2009). Best practices, standards and techniques for digitising library materials: A snapshot of library digitisation practices in the USA. *Online Information Review*, 28, 338–345. www.emeraldinsight.com/1468-4527.htm
- Otubelu, B. N. & Ume, L.E. (2015). Digitisation of library resources in academic libraries: challenges and implications. *IOSR Journal of Mobile Computing and Application*, 2(2) pp. 35-40
- Pandey, P. & Misra, R. (2014). Digitisation of library materials in academic libraries: Issues and Challenges. *Journal of Industrial and Intelligent Information*, 2(2).
- Reitz, J. M. (2004). One-shot. Dictionary for Library and Information Science. Westport, Connecticut: Libraries Unlimited. p. 499. ISBN 1-59158-075-7.
- Sreenivasulu, V. (2000). The role of a digital librarian in the management of digital information systems (DIS). *The Electronic Library*, 2000, 18(1), pp. 12–20. <http://eprints.rclis.org/6502/>
- Umar, A. M. & Shittu, M. (2012). Digitisation of library resources in Kashim Ibrahim library: processes, challenges and the impact on the services of the library. Being a paper presented at the Kaduna State chapter of the NLA/AGM conference on 12th Dec. 2012
- Usman, I. A. (2007). Digitisation of past question papers, dissertations and theses: A case study of 30 Nigerian University Libraries. *International Information and Library Review*. p229. <http://www.elsevier.com/locate/iilr>.
- Usman, I. A. & Iyun, A. M. (2007). *Greenstone Digital Library software: the librarian's role*. Paper presented at the national workshop on digitisation of Library Materials: processes and tools, organised by the National Library of Nigeria, at the University of Jos, Jos, Plateau State
- Yaya, J. A. & Adeeko, K. (2016). Digitisation of educational resources in Nigerian academic libraries: prospects, challenges and the way forward. *International Journal of Information Research and Review*, 3(1) pp. 1594-1600